

Concept Drift in Process Data: A Control Chart Approach and Methodology

Yoann Valero^{1,2}, Frédéric Bertrand¹, and Myriam Maumy¹

¹LIST3N, University of Technology of Troyes, 12 Rue Marie Curie, CS 42060, 10004 Troyes
Cedex, France

²QAD Process Intelligence, 12 rue de l'Aligre, 75012 Paris, France

Abstract

Process data commonly comes in the form of event logs, which record units going through said processes. An event log is made up of a unit identifier, activities through which units may pass, the time and date at which units go through these activities, as well as other possible descriptive variables. The sequence of events pertaining to a given unit is called its *journey*. Processes are subject to multiple variations, of multiple magnitude, and of multiple types. When these variations stack, or when a big enough variation occurs, concept drift is in effect. The difficulty lies in defining when variations are sufficient to alert for concept drift, as well as in a proper definition of concept drift with regards to this type of sequential data. We therefore propose a full methodology to establish control charts, specifically u charts and $EWMA$ charts, to follow complex drifts in process data, particularly in activity sequences. Our method monitors concept drift in an easy to implement way, and is easily interpretable even by non-statisticians.

Key Words: Concept Drift, Processes, Control Charts, Event logs

1. Introduction

This article focuses on the principle of concept drift in process data. In the broadest sense, concept drift is defined as a change in the statistical properties of the target variable of a predictive model. Several studies have already been carried out on this subject when applied to process data, and an inventory has been undertaken by the authors of [29]. A multitude of approaches and definitions are set out. Some use clustering and the evolution of clusters in order to detect drift. Others use statistical tests, others the conformity of process models like Petri nets [21] searched using classic process mining methods such as Heuristics Miner [32] or Fuzzy Miner [9]. These approaches vary in complexity, both in their implementation and in their use in a business context.

This article therefore provides a methodology for detecting concept drift in process data without a predictive model, in a way that is simple to implement and interpret, particularly in an industrial production and supply chain context.

To do so, we use Statistical Process Control (SPC) and control charts, mentioned in [8], [23] and [25] among others. These are used to monitor and diagnose drift in the production quality of machines as part of industrial processes. Using samples from the production process, they enable production quality to be checked by measurement or according to non-conformity criteria at selected stages of the process. They provide a formalism and a statistical approach to production quality drift, making it possible to estimate the type I risk, type II risk, and to express them in terms of the number of samples required on average for them to occur. It therefore seems quite natural to use such tools to measure not production drift in this case, but concept drift of process data.

This approach has already been used for concept drift control in streaming data in [18], and a type of control chart for time-varying dynamical systems in [22]. Another method based on the gradient of the log-likelihood of a supervised learning model is described in [33]. As the idea is for the method to be used in a production setting and for it to be quickly and easily understood by any operator, the use of simple control charts is favoured.

The method developed here first requires a reference period to be established, enabling the typical data generated by a process under normal operating conditions to be defined. Since we are opting for the use of control charts, we then focus on several ways of defining non-conformities in process data, as well as a means of measuring or counting them. These definitions then enable them to be measured and represented in measurement control charts, attribute control charts and control charts that weight past observations to identify longer, slower trends in concept drift. Each control chart is established following guidelines of national and international standards, in particular AFNOR [2, 3, 4, 5] and ISO [11, 12, 13, 14, 15] standards.

Let us follow with definitions related to process monitoring, as well as basics of statistical process control using control charts.

2. Definitions and data

The data most prevalent in process monitoring is in the form of event logs, which are records of events occurring in a process throughout time. We hereafter define a few concepts that are used in this paper as used standardly in process mining papers, such as [31] and [1].

Units circulating through a process are given a unique case identifier, and may go through a finite set of possible activities. Thus, let \mathcal{C} be the set of case identifiers, \mathcal{A} the set of all possible activities and \mathcal{T} the set of timestamps, which in our case is equivalent to \mathbb{R}^+ .

Definition 1 (Event). *An event $e_i \in \mathcal{E}$ is a tuple with at least 3 components: $e_i = (c_i, a_i, t_i)$, where $c_i \in \mathcal{C}$, $a_i \in \mathcal{A}$, and $t_i \in \mathcal{T}$ is its timestamp marking the start date and time of a_i . An event may contain other attributes, but these are not considered in this paper.*

We can then define functions $\pi_{\mathcal{C}}(e_i) = c_i$, $\pi_{\mathcal{A}}(e_i) = a_i$ and $\pi_{\mathcal{T}}(e_i) = t_i$ to extract the case identifier, activity and timestamp of a given event.

Definition 2 (Process instance). *A process instance, also called a case or a unit, is a finite sequence of events $\sigma = \langle e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n \rangle$, $e_i \in \mathcal{E}$ and $n = |\sigma|$, such that $\pi_{\mathcal{T}}(e_i) \leq \pi_{\mathcal{T}}(e_{i+1})$ if $n \geq 2$, and $\pi_{\mathcal{C}}(e_i) = \pi_{\mathcal{C}}(e_{i+1})$, $\forall i \in \llbracket 1, n-1 \rrbracket$. In other words, a process instance is the sequence of all events that share the same case identifier, chronologically ordered. The representative of all process instances sharing the same activity sequence is called a trace, which is a crucial notion in this article.*

Definition 3 (Event log). *An event log is a set of process instances such that each event contained in it is unique. Formally, an event log is therefore a collection of process instances $\{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \dots, \sigma_n\}$. Its size in terms of process instances is denoted as $|L|_{\sigma}$ and its size in terms of events is noted $|L|_e$, with $|L|_{\sigma} \leq |L|_e$.*

Table 1: Three process instances in Traffic fines event log

Case identifier	Activity	Timestamp
A1	Create Fine	2006-07-24
A1	Send Fine	2006-12-05
A100	Create Fine	2006-08-02
A100	Send Fine	2006-12-12
A100	Insert Fine Notification	2007-01-15
A100	Add penalty	2007-03-16
A100	Send for Credit Collection	2009-03-30
A10000	Create Fine	2007-03-09
A10000	Send Fine	2007-07-17
A10000	Insert Fine Notification	2007-08-02
A10000	Add penalty	2007-10-01
A10000	Payment	2008-09-09

Table 1 shows the first three process instances of the event log *Traffic fines* [19], also provided by the R[28] package `eventdataR`[17], part of the `bupaR` framework [16]. These first three process instances constitute an event log of lengths $|L|_{\sigma} = 3$ and $|L|_e = 12$, each line constituting an event.

The event logs used in this paper are the following:

- **Helpdesk**[26]: event log recording events related to a ticketing management process in a help desk at an Italian company, from January 2010 to November 2012.
- **Traffic fines**[19]: real-life event log of an information system managing road traffic fines. Timestamps range from June 2006 to March 2012.
- **BPI2012(W) and BPI2012**[27]: event log of a loan application process at a Dutch financial institute, containing three sub-processes. One of them, noted *W*, was tested on its own. It spans dates from October 2011 to March 2012.
- **BPI2017**[7]: event log containing data related to a loan application process at the same Dutch financial institute as in BPI2012, but set between January 2016 and February 2017.

3. Preliminaries on control charts

3.1 General principles

A control chart is used to study one or more characteristics that define the quality of a given production. It can be based on measurements such as the thickness of a part or the torsional strength of a material, it can be a count of non-conformities such as the number of scratches on paint, or conformity may be treated as a binary character depending on the presence / absence of a characteristic. There are control charts for each case.

Characteristics are measured in samples through time and placed on a chart where the horizontal axis is the rank of samples in time, and the vertical axis corresponds to the value of the studied characteristic. Each sample is thus represented as a point on a control chart. These charts also possess, typically, three lines:

- A center line, noted **CL**, which represents the nominal value of the studied characteristic when production is deemed stable and well tuned.
- A lower control limit, noted **LCL**, which represents the lowest the characteristic may reach before production is deemed out of control according to production standards.

- An upper control limit, noted **UCL**, which represents the highest the characteristic may reach before production is deemed out of control according to production standards.

One may also add two surveillance lines, noted **LSL** for the lower surveillance line and **USL** for the upper surveillance line. These serve as warning lines, only necessitating increased awareness on the production when samples are between a surveillance line and its corresponding control limit.

3.2 Types of control charts

Depending on the nature of the studied characteristic, noted X , multiple control charts are at our disposal:

Considering the last sample:

1. If X is quantitative, i.e. measurable, Shewhart charts [12] may be used. These charts usually follow the mean and the standard deviation of X , giving two charts called \bar{x} and S charts respectively.
2. If X is the presence or absence of a property, control charts by attributes [13] are adopted:
 - np charts count the number of non-conform entities in a sample.
 - u charts count the number of non-conformities on a single entity.

Considering a sequence of successive samples:

1. *EWMA* charts (Exponentially Weighted Moving Average) [15].
2. *CUSUM* charts (CUMulative SUM) [14].

3.3 Control chart efficiency

Let X and X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be independent identically distributed random variables (*iid*). We suppose that the point reported on the control chart is the mean $\bar{X} = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i$. the shift in production, noted δ , is defined by :

$$\delta = \frac{\mathbb{E}_1[X] - \mathbb{E}_0[X]}{\sqrt{\text{Var}_0(X)}},$$

with $\mathbb{E}_1[X]$ the expectation of X when production has shifted, and $\mathbb{E}_0[X]$ and $\text{Var}_0(X)$ the expectation and variance of X when production is at its baseline. We then have the two risks:

- Type I risk α of wrongly detecting a shift in production.
- Type II risk β of missing a shift in production.

We thus have two methods to assess the efficiency of control charts in terms of their ability to minimize both risks. The first are efficiency curves, which give the probability P_a of accepting a sample given a shift. The second is Average Run Length, noted *ARL*, which is defined as the average number of successive samples needed to get a point beyond control limits. We use typical notations used in ISO and AFNOR standards regarding *ARL*:

- ARL_0 is the ARL when $\delta = 0$, i.e. when the process is at its baseline. In other words, it is the average number of samples needed to observe a point out of control limits while the process is well tuned.
- ARL_1 is the ARL when $\delta = \delta_1 \neq 0$.

The aim is to obtain control charts with an ARL_0 as high as possible in order to avoid false alarms, with an ARL_1 as low as possible to quickly detect true shifts in production. For Shewhart charts, links between ARL and P_a are as follows:

$$\alpha = 1 - P_a(\delta = 0), \quad ARL_0 = \frac{1}{\alpha} = \frac{1}{1 - P_a(\delta = 0)},$$

$$\beta = P_a(\delta = \delta_1), \quad ARL_1 = \frac{1}{1 - \beta} = \frac{1}{1 - P_a(\delta = \delta_1)}.$$

These links allow to compare control charts for which we possess efficiency curves to charts for which we possess ARL , which is important to compare *EWMA* and *CUSUM* charts to Shewhart charts and charts for attributes, as it is difficult to calculate efficiency curves for *EWMA* and *CUSUM* charts.

Preliminaries now established, the following section details our method to use these tools in the context of concept drift for process data, distinguishing drift in activities and drift in durations.

4. Comparison period and reference period

Working with data instead of physical materials and machines, the notions of destructive sampling or the difficulty of sampling do not arise. The data becomes periodically available and is added to a history, enabling a new sample to be created. Furthermore, since the data is recorded electronically and the measurements are actually calculations performed by algorithms directly on the data, the reliability of the measuring equipment and operator error can be considered negligible – provided those algorithms are correctly coded.

This means that we can split an event log through time into successive *sub-logs*, which constitute our samples. Let r be the number of samples. For Shewhart charts, it is recommended to have enough observations in the samples so that $\sum_{i=1}^r n_i \geq 100$, n_i the size of a sample i . For attribute control charts, it is advisable to have $\sum_{i=1}^r n_i \geq 300$. As this lower limit is well below the size of the available data in our case, the question is rather to know what sample size to consider, which will condition the number of sub-logs into which the event log will be subdivided. This sample size should be considered as a function of the ARL_0 and ARL_1 preferred by the parties using these control charts. This implicitly means that the efficiency of these control charts is defined by the span of time sub-logs cover.

We split each event log according to the following rule: the size of a sub-log in terms of journeys is $\max \left\{ \left\lfloor \frac{|L|_e}{100} \right\rfloor, 50 \right\}$. So each event log is subdivided into 100 sub-logs, unless the sub-logs have sizes less than 50, in which case the sub-log size is set to 50. This leads to sub-logs with 50 journeys for *Helpdesk* on average, 100 for *Traffic fines*, 85 for *BPI2012 (w)*, 132 for *BPI2012*, and 278 for *BPI2017*.

We must now define a way to qualify and quantify reference periods in order to create our charts.

Generally speaking, each sub-log brings new traces, implying new, unseen before sequences of activities. We can then count how many new traces each successive sub-log brings to the previous sub-logs.

We expect a typical process to have the first sub-logs bringing almost exclusively new traces, with a downward trend until a point of stagnation is reached. Once this stagnation has been reached, the sub-logs prior to this stagnation constitute the comparison period, which contains all traces considered to be normal to occur in the process. The sub-logs in the stagnation phase constitute the normal regime of the process, contributing a more or less constant number of new traces to the event log,

which will be used to create the lines and limits of our control charts.

On figure 1, we can see for each event log that the number of new traces decreases as new sub-logs appear, but does not always reach 0. However, we might wonder whether this is an indication that the process is simply generating fewer traces, converging toward a single trace, with the exception of a few new traces. Figure 2 shows the number of traces contained in each sub-log, regardless of their novelty, and we can see that this number tends to be stable over time. This means that there tends to be the same variety of traces in sub-logs through time.

Even more interesting: if new traces are simply added, and the number of traces in each sub-log gravitates around the average, this may imply that the old traces disappear over time, to be replaced by new ones.

Let us go back to figure 1 to determine the periods of comparison and reference of our used processes. The elbows in these counts can be considered as follows:

- **Helpdesk:** the tendency is not clear but we can consider that the stable regime is reached from sub-log 40 onward. The comparison period is thus constituted of sub-logs 1 to 40, and the reference period of sub-logs 41 to 76.
- **Traffic fines:** its regime seems stable starting from sub-log 10. The comparison period is therefore made of sub-logs 1 to 10, and the reference period is made of sub-logs 11 to 90.
- **BPI2012 (W):** we see a clear decrease until sub-log 30 forming the comparison period, to then stabilize until sub-log 100 for the reference period.
- **BPI2012:** this event log shows an even more stable reference period. We see that the comparison period can be made of sub-logs 1 to 35, the next 65 sub-logs constituting the reference period.
- **BPI2017:** this event log shows a less clear reference period. We can establish the comparison period using sub-logs 1 to 25, but the following sub-logs show two separate plateaus. We can treat the whole remaining period as the reference period for simplicity's sake, as we do here. But one may also consider treating the first plateau as the reference period, and simply using the remaining points as a set of sub-logs to be plotted on the resulting charts.

With these periods defined, we finally assume that the comparison period corresponds to the initial state of the process. Then, the reference period corresponds to the phase when in-sample trace variety becomes roughly constant. Control charts can be used to determine the point at which the gap between a process's past and present becomes statistically significant.

Figure 1: Number of new traces brought by each successive sub-log in the used event logs

Figure 2: Number of traces in each successive sub-logs in the used event logs

5. Method for activities

5.1 Important considerations

Let us consider a process recorded in an event log L , comprising $|L|_e$ events, $|L|_\sigma$ journeys and $|L|_T$ traces. A first line of thought concerns what we can consider to be a new trace in the data. Let's imagine a journey whose trace would be the sequence of activities $\langle A, B, C \rangle$. Then imagine a new journey with the sequence of activities $\langle A, B, A, B, A, B, A, B, A, B, C \rangle$. These two sequences are different. Despite this, the second sequence shows no obvious deviation from the behaviour of the first, except for the repetition of the subsequence A, B (and therefore the transition from activity B to activity A).

Let's also consider datasets such as *BPI2012 (W)*. This has only 6 activities, but the repetitions give rise to a large number of traces compared with the number of journeys. In this case, given that the longest trace has 74 events, a new journey with just one additional repetition already observed would be considered a new trace, just like $\langle A, B, A, B, A, B, C \rangle$ or $\langle A, B, A, B, A, B, A, B, A, B, A, B, C \rangle$ to take up the previous example. It therefore seems sensible to compare the traces mainly once the repeats found in the comparison period have been removed, or "pruned". We keep all repetitions that are observed outside of the comparison period.

It is also possible to consider these pruned repetitions as a separate character to be studied: it may be interesting to follow the evolution of these repetitions.

The type of repetitions that we consider are "maximal repetitions" [6], which are simply repetitions which occur less in a sequence if extended once on the right, or once on the left.

Another consideration regarding repetitions concerns the order in which they are removed. Let's imagine that we remove repetitions in ascending order of sizes: it is possible that a large repetition contains several small ones, all of which are considered to be maximum. Removing the small repeats would leave a subsequence riddled with holes, giving a subsequence that would no longer be a repetition in itself. Artefacts of these large repetitions would then remain in the data. It therefore seems more sensible to remove repeats in descending order of sizes, in order to remove the largest repeated subsequences at once and refine the pruning as we go along.

Furthermore, a single activity can constitute a maximum repetition. It is sufficient for a single trace to contain a single maximum repetition of unit length for the corresponding activity to be removed from all the traces. If each activity were to constitute a maximum repetition at least once, we would end up with an empty event log once pruned. It is therefore important to consider only repetitions of size ≥ 2 .

Using the example above, the trace $\langle A, B, A, B, A, B, A, B, C \rangle$ can be pruned of the maximum repetition $\langle A, B, A, B \rangle$, of $\langle A, B, A \rangle$ and of $\langle A, B \rangle$. By removing them in descending order of size, only $\langle C \rangle$ remains. Similarly, the trace $\langle A, B, C \rangle$ is pruned of the repetition $\langle A, B \rangle$ since this is present in $\langle A, B, A, B, A, B, A, B, C \rangle$. This also leaves $\langle C \rangle$, and the objective is achieved: with the maximum repeats removed, these traces are identical.

5.2 Measure of drift in activities

Repetitions present in the traces of the comparison period are removed from all traces of all sub-logs, including future ones. In this way, traces are reduced to their skeleton. The only remaining repeats are those not observed in the comparison period.

Secondly, we can imagine that each activity appearing in an atypical place in these pruned traces could constitute a non-conformity. We already have pruned traces for the comparison period and the reference period. A good way of comparing them is to calculate their Damerau-Levenshtein distances [20, 24] in pairs, and for each trace from the reference period, to take the minimum observed distance. Thus, let T_C be the set of journeys in the comparison period, and let k be the index of the first journey outside the comparison period. For a journey σ_i with $k \leq i \leq |L|_\sigma$, we calculate :

$$\min_{\zeta \in T_C} d_{DL}(\sigma_i, \zeta).$$

where DL is the Damerau-Levenshtein distance. Since this distance takes account of edits (deletions, insertions, permutations) to get from one sequence of symbols to another, retaining the minimum distance for a journey in the reference period amounts to finding its closest counterpart among traces of the comparison period, and counting the number of points of divergence between the two. These points of divergence can be considered non-conformities in relation to the traces of the comparison period. Averaged over each sub-log, this number of non-conformities per unit is then used to calculate the reference values for the future control chart, namely its CL, LCL and UCL.

In our case, we are counting non-conformities by units. A u chart should therefore be used.

The choice of the u chart, as opposed to a c chart which counts the number of non-conformities per sample, is justified by the fact that u charts allow sample sizes to vary. Let us now present the fundamental principles of the u charts.

Let $c_0(n)$ (from the c charts) be the average number of non-conformities per sample of size n , established in a reference period. The index 0 indicates the reference period. The number of non-conformities per sample of size n_j follows a Poisson distribution parameterised by $c_0(n_j)$. We note $X_j \sim \mathcal{P}(c_0(n_j))$. We look at the number of non-conformities per unit, noted $U_j = \frac{X_j}{n_j}$. For this random variable, the expectation is:

$$\mathbb{E}_0[U_j] = \mathbb{E}_0 \left[\frac{X_j}{n_j} \right] = \frac{\mathbb{E}_0[X_j]}{n_j} = \frac{c_0(n_j)}{n_j} = u_0.$$

Likewise, for the variance:

$$\text{Var}(U_j) = \text{Var} \left(\frac{X_j}{n_j} \right) = \frac{\text{Var}(X_j)}{n_j^2} = \frac{c_0(n_j)}{n_j^2} \iff \sigma_{U_j,0} = \sqrt{\frac{c_0(n_j)}{n_j^2}} = \sqrt{\frac{u_0}{n_j}}.$$

The central line is $CL = u_0$, and the control limits are:

$$LCL = u_0 - 3\sqrt{\frac{u_0}{n_j}} \quad \text{and} \quad UCL = u_0 + 3\sqrt{\frac{u_0}{n_j}},$$

$$LSL = u_0 - 2\sqrt{\frac{u_0}{n_j}} \quad \text{and} \quad USL = u_0 + 2\sqrt{\frac{u_0}{n_j}}.$$

In practice, u_0 is estimated by counting the number of non-conformities in the samples of the reference period (here our reference period). Let $r \in \mathbb{N}^*$ be the number of samples (here sub-logs), and $i \in \{1, \dots, r\}$ a sample of size n_i . We denote c_i the number of non-conformities counted in the sample. Then:

$$u_0 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r c_i}{\sum_{i=1}^r n_i}.$$

These definitions and properties, taken from standard NF X 06-031-2 [3], enable us to draw up u charts for our sub-logs. It should be noted that despite the possibility of having variable sample sizes, it is recommended that this variability between sample sizes be limited to a maximum of 25%. Furthermore, although attribute control charts have lower monitoring and control limits, these do not in themselves constitute a warning. In fact, crossing the lower limits indicates a significant improvement in production (in this case, concept drift), since the number of non-conformities is well below the reference average. That said, it may be interesting, where possible, to explore the reasons for such improvements.

By applying these principles to our minimum Damerau-Levenshtein distances between journeys from the reference period, and the traces from the comparison period, all pruned of the repetitions observed during the comparison period, we obtain figure 3. This represents u charts corresponding to each event log, made up of points from the reference period. *Helpdesk* shows a majority of points at 0, indicating that the new traces observed in figure 2 are not, in general, made up of new

connections between activities or new repetitions. There is a sudden increase at the end of the period. A similar observation can be made for *Traffic fines*, and *BPI2012 (W)* shows no violation. *BPI2012* and *BPI2017*, however, show a good example of gradual concept drift: the number of traces per sub-log is stable, but new traces replace old ones. In both cases, there is indeed a gradual increase in the number of non-conformities per unit, until violations are reached.

Figure 3: u charts of non-conformities established with the reference period on all used event logs

In terms of the efficiency of the u chart, we can calculate efficiency curves, which give the probability of production acceptance as a function of the actual proportion of non-conformities per unit. In a u chart, the shift δ is $\frac{u - u_0}{\sqrt{u_0}}$. With this control chart, the acceptable limit for non-conformities is the

UCL. We therefore consider the deviation $\delta_1 = \frac{UCL - u_0}{\sqrt{u_0}}$. In a sample of size n , the number of non-conformities per sample required to exceed the UCL is:

$$k_1 = E(nLCS) + 1,$$

where $E(\cdot)$ is the integer part function. Although samples can be of variable sizes, limiting their variability to a maximum of 25% makes it possible to replace n by their mean $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^r n_i$.

From k_1 , we can deduce that the maximum number of non-conformities acceptable in a sample is $k_1 - 1$. Therefore, the efficiency curve, defined by the probability of acceptance P_a , is:

$$P_a(n, u) = \sum_{k=0}^{k_1-1} e^{-nu} \frac{(nu)^k}{k!},$$

where u is the number of non-conformities per unit. We can see that the efficiency curve depends on both n and k_1 . We can thus calculate P_a when the process under study has not drifted, and when a deviation is present. We can then calculate the corresponding ARL_0 and ARL_1 .

Table 2 lists the efficiency of the control charts shown in figure 3. Here we observe k_1 , the number of non-conformities required in a sub-log to exceed the UCL, which depends on the size of the

Table 2: Efficiency of u charts for concept drift of activity sequences

Event logs	k_1	δ_1	$\mathbf{P}_a(\delta_0)$	$\mathbf{P}_a(\delta_1)$	α	β	ARL_0	ARL_1
Helpdesk	3	4.05	0.981	0.47	0.019	0.47	53.24	1.89
Traffic fines	4	3.33	0.99	0.53	0.01	0.53	105.13	2.14
BPI2012 (W)	5	2.92	0.995	0.60	0.005	0.60	217.59	2.51
BPI2012	53	0.51	0.998	0.51	0.002	0.51	422.23	2.06
BPI2017	101	0.35	0.998	0.53	0.002	0.53	569.01	2.11

sub-logs. We have the derangement δ_1 associated with the UCL, followed by the probability of acceptance of a sub-log without drift and with drift corresponding to the UCL. The associated risks α and β are calculated, and the ARL_0 and ARL_1 are given. Typically, what we deduce from this table is that the control charts created with the default method of sub-log sizes described above are conservative in terms of drift alerts. There is a very high probability of acceptance in the event of no drift, very close to 1, but a probability of acceptance of around 0.5 in the event of drift corresponding to the UCL. This gives high ARL_0 values, indicating that it takes a significant number of successive sub-logs with no drift before a false alarm is reached. On the other hand, it takes an average of 2 to 3 drift-free samples to detect a drift corresponding to the UCL. This may not be a problem, but it does depend to a large extent on how long it takes for future sub-logs to become available: missing an adjustment on 2 sub-logs may be less serious if they are available every day, as opposed to weekly or monthly availability.

These charts are nonetheless functional, analysable and, above all, adjustable so that the α and β risks (and therefore the ARL_0 and ARL_1) can be adjusted in line with expectations in the field.

The control charts in figure 3 have been calculated, but a library R can be used to produce all sorts with ease: the library `qcc`[30]. This is used for the rest of this section, for convenience. Among other things, it makes it easy to create *EWMA* and *CUSUM* charts. As explained in section 3.2, these charts take account of past observations and allow longer-term trends to be monitored. This can be important in determining whether a violation on a u chart, for example, corresponds to a one-off accident or is more symptomatic of a drift over time.

In the following, *EWMA* charts will be preferred to *CUSUM* charts. The tool developed in this article is not necessarily aimed at operators and users familiar with statistical process control, and the *EWMA* chart is easier to understand than the *CUSUM* chart, which can display two points for the same sample. In addition, the authors of [10] show that *EWMA* charts can be more effective than *CUSUM* charts in the case of a smaller than expected drift. This is an important advantage given the β risk observed in previous u charts.

An *EWMA* chart studies a characteristic assumed to be gaussian with constant variance. More precisely, it is assumed that the mean is constant, before going out of adjustment and becoming constant again in this out of adjustment. This last assumption is not very realistic in an industrial process, and is even less so in our case, but the tool remains convenient for its use as a support for the u chart.

We define the random variables $X, X_1, \dots, X_n \stackrel{\text{iid}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$. An *EWMA* chart evaluates the random variable Z_i :

$$Z_i = \lambda \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} (1-\lambda)^j \bar{X}_{i-j} + (1-\lambda)^i m_0,$$

with λ a smoothing parameter, $Z_0 = m_0$ the mean in baseline period, and \bar{X}_{i-j} the mean of the character in sample $i-j$. The closer λ is to 0, the more past samples influence the value of Z_i . Control limits are:

$$LCL = m_0 - L \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2-\lambda}} \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}, \quad UCL = m_0 + L \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2-\lambda}} \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}.$$

Even though the studied character in our case is not gaussian but a count, it is possible to approximate it by a normal distribution since our sample sizes are sufficient to allow it. Let c be the average number of non-conformities in a sub-log, noted c_0 when there is no drift. The number of non-conformities in a sample can be approximated by a $\mathcal{N}(c, \sqrt{c_0})$ distribution. We thus have the limits:

$$LCL = c_0 - L\sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2-\lambda}}\sqrt{c_0}, \quad UCL = c_0 + L\sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2-\lambda}}\sqrt{c_0}.$$

To illustrate the use of *EWMA* charts on large scales of time (months, years), choosing a low λ may help bring out long-term trends from the data. We thus chose $\lambda = 0.05$ for all our *EWMA* charts since event logs span years of process history.

On figure 4, we have *EWMA* charts for non-conformities in *Traffic fines* (top graphic) and *BPI2012 (W)* (bottom graphic). Like the previous *u* chart, *BPI2012 (W)* shows no particular drift throughout the whole span of its history, we can thus conclude that no significant drift occurred both punctually and long term.

However, *Traffic fines* shows an increase of the number of non-conformities from around the 60th sub-log until the end of the recorded period, crossing the UCL for the last few sub-logs. This confirms the trend observed in its corresponding *u* chart.

Figure 4: *EWMA* charts for non-conformities in *Traffic fines* and *BPI2012(W)*

6. Measure of drift in durations

With the most complex part of the methodology established, drift of journey durations can now be easily monitored. A first approach is to measure total durations: in each sub-log, we can calculate the average total duration of journeys and follow its evolution over time.

This is a quantitative characteristic, so we need to use Shewhart charts of the average, described in [12]. These charts can be used to monitor measurement averages, and are generally accompanied by *S* charts to check the stability of the standard deviation of the measured values. Adding an *EWMA* chart can also be used to check the drift of these durations over longer-term trends.

A much simpler method than for the activities is available to us: the comparison period, corresponding to the sub-logs before the bend observed in figure 1, can now be used as a reference period for

calculating the limits and the centre line of a control chart. The sub-logs present in this period are simply used to calculate the average of the total durations (also called "total throughput times") of the journeys they contain, which then form the control charts. The journeys in the reference period can be used as new data to be placed on the charts.

Thus, for a given journey $\sigma = \langle e_1, \dots, e_k \rangle$, we simply calculate its total duration $\Delta_\sigma = \pi_{\mathcal{T}}(e_k) - \pi_{\mathcal{T}}(e_1)$. In the case of two timestamps, we calculate $\Delta_\sigma = \pi'_{\mathcal{T}}(e_k) - \pi_{\mathcal{T}}(e_1)$.

The calculation of the centre line, i.e. the reference average, noted μ_0 and estimated by m_0 , is simply done by calculating the average of the sub-log averages in the comparison period. So, if this period consists of r sub-logs, we have:

$$m_0 = \sum_{i=1}^r \overline{\Delta}_i,$$

where $\overline{\Delta}_i$ is the average of all total durations in sub-log i . For an estimation of the reference standard deviation σ_0 estimated with s_0 , with the same r sub-logs of size n in the comparison period, we have:

$$s_0^2 = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^r s_i^2, \quad \text{with } s_i^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^J (\Delta_{i,j} - \overline{\Delta}_i)^2.$$

As per [2] and [12], we have for control limits:

$$LCL = \mu_0 - \Phi_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \frac{\sigma_0}{\sqrt{n}} \quad \text{et} \quad UCL = \mu_0 + \Phi_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \frac{\sigma_0}{\sqrt{n}},$$

with α the chosen type I α risk and $\Phi_{\mathcal{N}(0,1)}^{-1}(\cdot)$ the quantile function of a $\mathcal{N}(0,1)$ distribution. Typically, for control limits, this risk is chosen at $\alpha = 0,0027$. Thus, the $1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}$ quantile of a $\mathcal{N}(0,1)$ is ~ 3 . In the case of surveillance limits, we have $\alpha = 0,0455$, for a quantile of ~ 2 .

On figure 5, the top graph shows a Shewhart control chart of the mean calculated from the comparison period of *BPI2012 (W)*. The central line is at 11 days. The points placed before the vertical dotted line correspond to the sub-logs of this comparison period, while the following ones are in the reference period. A clear decrease is observed from sub-log 80 onward.

An *EWMA* chart of these average durations can be interesting. This is the subject of the middle graph of figure 5. Here we see a period between samples 50 and 89 that is entirely out of bounds, exceeding the *UCL*. On the chart *xbar*, only 2 points are out of range in this period. It therefore seems that the upward trend in total times is in fact a long-term trend. The same drastic decrease in total times can be seen in the latest sub-logs.

Since *EWMA* charts require the assumption of a constant standard deviation, a standard deviation chart must be drawn up. In this case, standard NFX 06-031-1 proposes the following control limits:

$$LCL = \frac{\sigma_0}{\sqrt{n-1}} \sqrt{F_{\chi_{n-1}^2}^{-1} \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} \right)} \quad \text{et} \quad UCL = \frac{\sigma_0}{\sqrt{n-1}} \sqrt{F_{\chi_{n-1}^2}^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2} \right)},$$

with $F_{\chi_{n-1}^2}^{-1}(\cdot)$ the quantile function of a χ_{n-1}^2 distribution. The α risk remains the same as previously stated for control and surveillance limits.

On figure 5, the bottom graph shows the *S* chart for total times in *BPI2012 (W)*. We can see a certain stability despite a few violations, followed by a drastic drop over the last few sub-logs. As the standard deviation cannot be considered constant over this period, the *EWMA* chart cannot be interpreted correctly for these last sub-logs. It would also be interesting to investigate the reason for this drop in standard deviation, which is seen as positive since total durations vary less and less.

Figure 5: *xbar*, *EWMA* and *S* charts for total throughput times in *BPI2012 (W)*

7. Conclusion

This work allows us to create control charts to monitor punctual and long-term drifts in process data in two ways: by monitoring drifts in the sequence of activities, and drifts in throughput times.

A first remark concerns the difference in treatment between activities and durations. Controlling concept drift in activities requires a basis for comparison, which means that the first sub-logs cannot be used to construct the boundaries and centre lines of the control charts. In addition, a detail needs to be taken into account: the period described as stagnating may not actually be all that stable in the sense of transitions between activities: if new traces appear and replace the old ones, a constant drift is in action in the controlled process. The stagnation period, used to construct the control charts, is therefore considered to be the reference period despite the drift already at work in the data.

However, the situations encountered are never quite so clear-cut: old traces can reappear further in time, and an often non-negligible proportion of new traces are only one-offs, constituting unique, atypical appearances. The method is therefore, in itself, a compromise between constant drift and the reality on the ground.

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